

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Implementation of leadership style to improve the quality of health services in hospitals: Literature review

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Abstract

Hospitals are health care institutions or agencies that organize comprehensive individual health services by providing inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services. The organization of the hospital is expected to provide affordable, quality health services, and optimal results to obtain high quality health service results. Achieving good hospital service quality can be achieved through good team performance as well. In the preparation of good team performance, it is necessary to choose the right leadership style in an organization. The organization in achieving its goals requires the function and role of the leader. The purpose of this study was to identify the implementation of leadership styles that can improve the quality of health services in hospitals. The method of research in this study is a qualitative research design with a literature study. Articles were searched through three data sources, namely PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar using the keywords "leadership style" AND "hospital quality". The articles used were published in the last five years, from 2019 to 2023. The study was limited to quantitative and qualitative research methods, but there were no restrictions on specific regions or countries. The results of the study found that the leadership style used can improve the quality of health services in hospitals. The quality of human resource performance is one of the main factors in improving the quality of service in hospitals. There are many leadership styles implemented in hospitals, including democratic, transformational, transactional, authentic, and directive leadership styles. The application of leadership styles must be adjusted to the conditions of the team members.

Keywords: Leadership style; Health Service; Quality; Hospital; Organization

1. Introduction

Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2020 defines a hospital as a health care institution or agency that organizes comprehensive individual health services by providing inpatient, outpatient, and emergency services. The Indonesian Ministry of Health states that the main task of establishing hospitals is to organize health services effectively and efficiently by prioritizing healing and recovery in an integrated manner to improve, prevent, and carry out referrals. The organization of hospitals is expected to provide affordable, quality health services, and optimal results to obtain high quality health service results.

In the book *Philosophy and Theory of Leadership*, leadership is the ability to influence other people, subordinates, or groups and the ability to direct the behavior of subordinates or groups^[1]. Leadership can also be defined as the art of influencing others to cooperate based on the leader's ability to guide others in achieving the group's desired goals. Organizations in achieving their goals require the function and role of the leader.

Quality of service is a service provided by a profession in accordance with standards that are carried out thoroughly according to patient needs^[2]. Indicators of service outcomes, such as patient incident rates, drug administration error rates, patient satisfaction levels, and blood draw error rates ^[2]. Law Number 40 of 2009 states that hospitals are

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required to carry out accreditation periodically at least once every three years. Based on this, hospital accreditation is very important for assessing service quality and hospital quality.

Human resources play an important role in the quality of health services in hospitals to support optimal accreditation results. In organizing human resources, hospitals need leaders to achieve these goals. A hospital needs an effective leader, who has the advantage of influencing its members [3]. Based on this, researchers designed this study to identify the implementation of leadership styles that can improve the quality of health services in hospitals.

2. Material and methods

The method that researchers used in writing this article was a literature review. Data was collected through three data sources, namely PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. Articles can be written in English or Indonesian. The keywords that researchers used in the study were "leadership style" AND "hospital quality". Article searches are limited to the latest articles, so the publication year is limited to the last 5 years, from 2019 to 2023. The use of articles in the form of original articles, full text, and open access. Articles were selected based on the purpose of writing, namely to determine the effect of leadership style on hospital service quality. The study used, namely articles that discuss the application of leadership styles in nurse performance to improve the quality of hospital service quality. The limitation of this study is only on quantitative and qualitative research methods, but there are no restrictions on specific regions or countries. In this research method by searching and collecting some literature and then examined in depth through a detailed way so that there is a good final result and in accordance with what is expected. Researchers selected eight articles that were considered relevant to the topic of the research discussion and put them together to draw conclusions in the literature review.

3. Results and discussion

Based on the results of searching for articles in various reference sources, the researcher obtained a research location in the hospital conducted in 4 countries. Details of the location research used by the study, including Indonesia (n=3), Jordan (n=2), Kuwait (1), and Canada (n=1). Year of article publication is at the level of 2019 to 2023, with details of three articles 2019 to 2023, with details of three articles published in 2019, one article in 2020, one article in 2021, and two articles in 2022. From, seven articles that fit the inclusion criteria inclusion criteria were written using quantitative research methods with various research methods, including descriptive, cross-sectional, correlation, observational analytic, and retrospection. The most widely used research sample was conducted on 1,626 health workers in six hospitals in Kuwait, while the least sample used was 80 workers at Wiyung Hospital Sejahtera Hospital. Most of the articles obtained by researchers came from Google Scholar and some articles obtained sourced from PubMed and ScienceDirect.

Table 1 List of articles

Author Name (Year)	Title	Research Methods	Sample/Population	Research Location	Results
Rasmun and Edi Sukamto (2019) [4]	Democratic Leadership Can Improve Motivation and Nursing Performance in Inpatient Wards at RSUD IE Moeis Samarinda	Descriptive correlation research design.	89 nurses at RSUD IE Moeis Samarinda	RSUD IE Moeis Samarinda	The head of the room in the ward who has a democratic leadership style has nurses who perform better than those in the ward whose leadership style is not democratic. This is evidenced by the OR value of 0.417.
Alloubani, et all (2019) [5]	Leadership Styles Influence on the Quality of Nursing Care	Cross-sectional, descriptive, and correlation research study design.	There were 400 respondents, including 50 nurse managers, 150 nursing staff,	Hospitals in the vicinity of the researcher.	There is a positive correlation between transformational leadership style with leadership outcomes and quality of nursing care. This is evidenced

			and 200 patients.		by the acquisition of the highest Pearson correlation value among other leadership styles, namely 0.856 (leadership outcomes), 0.789 (effectiveness), 0.759 (more effort), 0.811 (satisfaction), and 0.877 (quality of care).
Popy Puspitasari and Ratna Dwi Wulandari (2019) [6]	The Influence of Leadership Style on Employee Discipline in Wiyung Sejahtera Hospital	Quantitative research design with analytic observations.	80 workers at Wiyung Sejahtera Hospital.	Wiyung Sejahtera Hospital	The majority of leadership styles used are directive leadership styles, with research results as much as 31.25%. Supportive and achievement leadership styles have a slight difference in value with directive, namely 87.5% and 88.2%, while participative leadership style has the lowest value, which is as much as 50%.
Suliman, et all (2020) [7]	Effect of Nurse Manager's Leadership Styles on Predicted Nurse Turnover	Descriptive research design, cross-sectional, and correlation study.	280 nurses in public sector hospitals and one teaching hospital in northern Jordan.	Hospitals in Jordan	A total of 89% of the total respondents were of the opinion that transactional leadership style is a commonly used leadership style among nurse managers. In addition, transformational style was considered to reduce predicted nurse turnover, whereas passive-avoidant and transactional leadership styles had no significant effect on this.
AlFadhlah adn Elamir (2021) [8]	Organizational Culture, Quality of Care, and Leadership Style in Government General Hospitals in Kuwait: A Multimethod Study	Cross-sectional and retrospective quantitative research design	The 1,626 respondents were drawn from a population of 9,863 health workers in six hospitals.	Six hospitals in Kuwait.	A total of 60.5% to 80.5% applied transformational leadership style in the six hospitals studied. This study revealed that transformational leadership style has an influence on service quality and showed a positive and insignificant relationship between generic quality

					indicators and transformational style.
Tate, et al (2022) ^[9]	Authentic Leadership, Organizational Culture, and the Effect of Hospital Quality Management Practices on Quality of Care and Patient Satisfaction	Cross-sectional study design	226 Nurse manager.	A hospital in Canada.	Authentic leadership styles and hospital development cultures can improve quality management practices, quality of care, and patient satisfaction. Organizations implementing an authentic leadership style and/or group culture should target employee engagement, autonomy, and teamwork.
Puspita, et al (2022) ^[10]	Transformational Leadership and Competence to Increase Motivation and its Impact on Nurse Performance	Descriptive and verification research design with a quantitative approach.	90 nurses at Dewi Sri Karawang Hospital.	Dewi Sri Karawang Hospital.	Nurses' work motivation has a value of 70.18%, indicating that the work motivation of nurses at Dewi Sri Hospital is determined by the transformational leadership style and nurse competence. Good nurse performance can improve the quality of service in the hospital.

Based on this literature review, it can be seen that the leadership style used can improve the quality of health services in hospitals. The quality of human resource performance is one of the main factors in improving the quality of service in hospitals. Work motivation plays an important role in the quality of human resource performance in an organization. The higher the work motivation, the better the quality of performance shown. This also applies vice versa, the lower the work motivation, the worse the quality of work shown. The level of work motivation is strongly influenced by the leadership style applied by each hospital. In addition, leadership style can also affect teamwork between nurses and employees from the hospital. Communication and cohesiveness established in good teamwork will reduce errors in work carried out by each individual or group. This situation will build trust and the level of patient satisfaction with the quality of service in the hospital.

From various articles used as sources by researchers, many leadership styles are implemented in hospitals, including democratic, transformational, transactional, authentic, and directive leadership styles. Each of these articles states that there is an influence between the leadership styles applied by the manager or head of the hospital room. Democratic leadership style is human-oriented leadership and provides efficient guidance to its team members or followers^[1]. Leadership with a democratic style can improve nurse performance because there is coordination of work on all subordinates by emphasizing a sense of internal responsibility and good cooperation. Leaders with a transformational style act as leaders who motivate or encourage members to provide maximum performance, while the role of leaders in the transactional leadership style has a caregiver role and centers on the implementation of daily operations in the organization ^[5].

Leaders with authentic leadership styles have a role in supporting team members' freedom to make decisions and help build trust, resulting in increased performance participation and involvement in quality improvement with managers and team members ^[9]. Directive leadership style is how leaders direct their members by giving orders or specific tasks to team members or subordinates, making important decisions, and being involved in their implementation ^[11]. This

style of leadership tends to be one-way regardless of the opinions of subordinates because the leader acts as the center of information in a team and determines decision making. The application of leadership style must be adjusted to the conditions of the team members. Leaders must be able to choose a suitable leadership style so that the performance of team members can improve so that the quality of service in the hospital also increases.

4. Conclusion

The conclusion that can be drawn from this article is that the leadership style used can improve the quality of health services in hospitals. The quality of human resource performance is one of the main factors in improving the quality of service in hospitals. There are many leadership styles implemented in hospitals, including democratic, transformational, transactional, authentic, and directive leadership styles. The application of leadership styles must be adjusted to the conditions of the team members. Leaders must be able to choose a suitable leadership style so that the performance of team members can increase so that the quality of service in the hospital also increases.

Compliance with ethical standards

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